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European forum of the software research community

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Abstract:	These set of reports will present the results from the analysis on software, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity. This is the result of Task 3.1.
Keyword List:	Open Source Software Foundations, Open Source Software Developers, Open Source Software, Open Source Software Development
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Terms and abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
OS	Open Source
OSS	Open Source Systems
OSPOs	Open Source Programme Offices
PSD2	Payments Services Derivative 2 of the European Union

Executive Summary

This Landscape Report deliverable is the second and final in a series of two Reports, meant to describe the landscape surrounding the SWForum and the current existing and successful structures, which can provide model elements for the final form of the SWForum. It has been designed to be a follow-on to the Landscape Report 1 and represents an analysis of the 106 Open Source Foundations identified and found on the OSS Foundations GitHub webpage: <https://som-research.github.io/OSSFFoundations/#/>.

The deliverable also includes an analysis of a number of key parameters identified by the SWForum partners, a clustering exercise that groups the different organisations in an easily understandable structure, some explanation of the 5 most important organisations and finally some conclusions and recommendations that are relevant for the SWForum project and community.

1 Introduction

As a follow up on the first version of the Landscape reports, this deliverable has been focused on the analysis of the existing Open Source Community organisations, their metrics organised under a set of selected parameters with the objective of deriving some lessons learnt and conclusions of relevance for SWForum.eu community and its sustainability.

In order to provide a more complete picture of the Open Source Community organisations that can be used to benchmark SWForum activities, 106 open source organisations were identified and studied based upon this database: <https://som-research.github.io/OSSFfoundations/#/>

There was already a first set of parameters identified in grouping the organisations based upon the following:

- 1) International Scope
- 2) Independence
- 3) Transparency
- 4) Software Products Support

Interesting to note that quite a significant number of the organisations have either been “wound up” or are no longer active. Some of the reasons for this could be clearly related to the pandemic, but also related to the evolution of software products in differing directions.

1.1 Document structure

The deliverable is structured in two main parts:

- 1) Details and Analysis Charts of Each Open Source Organisation.
- 2) Conclusions and Concepts and Ideas Resulting from the Analysis, which could be interesting for SWForum to consider.

1.2 About this deliverable

The deliverable has taken each organisation identified and then analysed the organisation based upon a number of parameters in addition to the first set of parameters noted above. When there is not sufficient information available, the parameter is not included in the table.

These additional parameters as analysed include:

- 1) Internal Structure and Governance Model
 - a. Membership
 - b. Member Development Activities
 - c. Business Model
 - d. Governance Model
- 2) Engagement
 - a. Number of Projects
 - b. Number of Contributors
 - c. Number of Licenses
 - d. Type of Licenses

With, as previously mentioned, the initial parameters of:

- 1) International Scope
- 2) Independence
- 3) Transparency
- 4) Software Products Support

Furthermore, a clustering exercise of the Open Source organisations was conducted in order to identify a number of the key attributes associated with the organisations. It is important to note that the organisations can be in more than one cluster.

The Clusters were grouped as follows:

- 1) International (57 orgs) or Regional Scope (12 orgs)
- 2) Product / Framework / and/or Technology Dependent (40 orgs)
- 3) Generic Operating Systems (OS) – (24 orgs)
- 4) SWForum Pillars:
 - a. Digital Infrastructures (2 orgs)
 - b. Operating Systems (10 orgs)
 - c. Software Technologies (22 orgs)
 - d. Special Application Domains (20 orgs)
- 5) Focused Upon Specific Licenses (27 orgs)

1.3 Brief Commentary on the Pros and Cons of Open Source Software

Open source software has several advantages and disadvantages, which are important to consider when deciding whether to use it for a particular project or organization. Here are some of the main pros and cons of open source software:

1.3.1 Pros of Open Source Software

1. **Cost:** One of the main advantages of open source software is that it is typically available for free or at a significantly lower cost than proprietary software. This can be particularly beneficial for organizations that have limited budgets for software development or acquisition.
2. **Flexibility:** Open source software is often highly customizable and flexible, which can make it easier to adapt to the specific needs of a particular project or organization. Developers can modify the source code to add new features or functionality, or to address bugs and other issues.
3. **Community support:** Open source software is often developed and maintained by a large community of developers and users, who contribute their time and expertise to help improve the software. This can lead to a more collaborative and supportive development environment, and can also help to ensure that the software remains up-to-date and secure.
4. **Transparency:** Open source software is typically developed in a transparent and open manner, with the source code freely available for anyone to view and modify. This can help to promote trust and accountability, as users can see exactly how the software works and what it is doing.

1.3.2 Cons of Open Source Software

1. **Support:** While open source software often has a large and active community of developers, there may be limited formal support available for users who encounter issues or need assistance. This can be particularly challenging for organizations that rely on software for critical business functions.

2. **Compatibility:** Open source software may not be compatible with other proprietary software or platforms, which can create challenges when integrating different systems or tools.
3. **Complexity:** Open source software can be highly customizable and flexible, but this can also lead to increased complexity and technical challenges. Developers may need specialized skills and expertise to effectively modify and customize the software.
4. **Security:** While open source software is often developed with a focus on security and transparency, there is still the risk of vulnerabilities and other security issues. It is important to regularly update and maintain open source software to ensure that it remains secure and stable.

These are just a few of the main pros and cons of open source software. Ultimately, the decision to use open source software will depend on the specific needs and requirements of a particular project or organization.

2 Analysis of the Open Source Organisations based upon publicly available information

2.1 List of Active Organisations & Details

These tables / charts are based upon the websites and public information concerning the 106 open source organisations identified in:

<https://som-research.github.io/OSSFoundations/#/>.

Not all of the parameters were possible to analyse for each organisation as not all of the information is public. Furthermore, quite a number of the organisations identified have since “folded” or become inactive (moved to the Annex). This could be partly the result of the pandemic situation and also the evolution of open source software in differing directions. In addition, some of the organisations were also determined to be “out of scope” for our analysis and this was also noted in the tables / charts (which all have been moved to the Annex).

Table 1. Analysis of the OS organisations

.NET FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://dotnetfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	The .NET Foundation is an independent, non-profit organization established to support an open-source ecosystem around the .NET platform.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors (Board members should expect to commit 60 hours per month to .NET Foundation board commitments) + Technical steering group			
BUSINESS MODEL	Fee-based (see membership)			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solicitation of Membership applications 			
PROJECTS	124			
Licenses	They say “open source”			
APACHE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.apache.org/foundation/			
ABOUT	The mission of the Apache Software Foundation (ASF) is to provide software for the public good. They provide services and support for many software project communities consisting of individuals who choose to participate in ASF activities.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Nine-member board to run the foundation, to set policy, and to ensure it is carried out. These members appoint a number of officers to oversee the day-to-day operations of the Foundation. Project Management Committees			

	(PMCs), made up of individuals who have shown merit and leadership within ASF projects, govern those projects.			
BUSINESS MODEL	a) Sponsorship (differed levels form platinum 150k\$ per year to Bronze 6k\$ per year) b) Open donations from individuals; c) non-monetary (contributing to projects).			
MEMBERSHIP	<input type="checkbox"/> By invitation, Existing members propose and vote on candidates for membership (mainly based on meritocracy with respect to contribution to the projects). <input type="checkbox"/> Meritocracy			
PROJECTS	Around 350 projects			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	Committers are people with an Apache committer account, whereas authors may be any person that has contributed code to an Apache project. (8877 committers up to 2022)			
Licenses	Apache License, Version 2.0 (mainly)			
ASSOCIACAO SOFTWARE LIVRE				
WEB SITE	http://associacao.softwarelivre.org/			
ABOUT	OS association in Brasil. Their mission is to disseminate the benefits of using OSS.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors			
MEMBERSHIP	Only for physical persons that need to be approved by the Board of Directors.			
BSD FUND				
WEB SITE	https://bsdfund.org/			
ABOUT	BSD Fund is a reputation-based sponsorship program operated by Michael Dexter through Gainframe LLC of Oregon			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	None, managed by the owner.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Find sponsors			
MEMBERSHIP	Sponsorship			
PROJECTS	Approximately, 10 projects (OUT OF SCOPE)			
BENETECH				
WEB SITE	https://www.benotech.org/			
ABOUT	Non-profit organization with a pure focus on developing software for social good.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N

GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors + Advisory Council			
BUSINESS MODEL	Selling technological products			
MEMBERSHIP	Membership + volunteers (social good)			
BLENDER FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.blender.org/blenderorg/blender-foundation/			
ABOUT	The Blender Foundation (2002) is an independent public benefit organization with the purpose to provide a complete, free and open source 3D creation pipeline, managed by public projects on blender.org.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership and donations and supported by two other companies (institute and studio).			
MEMBERSHIP	For individuals. Different levels form 5€ month to 250 €/month). Also corporate. One time donations are also accepted			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	Around 500			
Licenses	Number: 1			
	Type: GNU General Public License			
CENTER FOR THE CULTIVATION OF TECHNOLOGY				
WEB SITE	https://www.techcultivation.org/			
ABOUT	It is a German charitable non-profit host organization for international Free Software projects.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	Services provision			
MEMBERSHIP	No			
CLOUD FOUNDRY FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.cloudfoundry.org/foundation/			
ABOUT	Independent non-profit open source organization formed to sustain the development, promotion and adoption of Cloud Foundry as the industry standard.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Governing Board Members who are accountable for strategic direction and business governance of Cloud Foundry Foundation and Technical Oversight Committee. 			
BUSINESS MODEL	Products/services etc.			

MEMBERSHIP	Corporate membership (different levels)			
DJANGO SOFTWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.djangoproject.com/foundation/			
ABOUT	Non-profit foundation to promote, support, and advance its open-source project: the Django Web framework			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors + members			
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership + support for events			
MEMBERSHIP	<p>Corporate members and Individual members (from platinum to Bronze, different levels);</p> <p>The Board of the Django Software Foundation invites people to become members after they establish some reputation through contributions to the community. All Django core developers are automatically invited to become members;</p> <p>Solicitation of Membership applications to corporations.</p>			
PROJECTS	1 project			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	2295			
Licenses	Redistribution and use in source and binary forms, with or without modification, are permitted/provided under some conditions.			
DOCUMENT FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.documentfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	Charitable German Foundation promoting libreoffice.org			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors + board of trustees (all members based on meritocracy) + Advisory board (fees) + membership committee.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations + advisory board members fees			
MEMBERSHIP	<p>Membership of the foundation will be open to any individual, encourage corporate participation, e.g. by sponsoring individuals to work as equals alongside other contributors in the community;</p> <p>Solicitation of Membership applications.</p>			
PROJECTS	Yes, different levels (Strategic, Contributor, associate, committers)			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	218 members			
ECLIPSE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.eclipse.org/org/foundation/			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products

	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors + Eclipse councils + staff			
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership fees + services			
MEMBERSHIP	There are different levels (Strategic, Contributor, associate, committers); Member portal.			
F# SOFTWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://foundation.fsharp.org/			
ABOUT	Non-for-profit organization to promote, protect, and advance the F# programming language			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of trustees elected by members and officers appointed by them.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership fees + donations			
MEMBERSHIP	Yes, Member, sustainer members and sponsor members (organizations)			
PROJECTS	113 projects			
FINTECH OPEN SOURCE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.finos.org/			
ABOUT	Open-Source Solutions for Financial Services			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Executive Director+ Governing Board (elected by members)			
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership fees			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate and regular • Access to board 			
PROJECTS	47 projects			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	1000+			
FREE KNOWLEDGE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://freeknowledge.eu/			
ABOUT	Non-profit organisation that fosters equal access to tools for production and exchange of knowledge in all areas of society			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Small Board			
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations + services about free knowledge			

MEMBERSHIP	No			
FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.fsf.org/			
ABOUT	Non-profit with a worldwide mission to promote computer user freedom.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors, and voting members			
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership fees + individual donations + products (merchandising mainly)			
MEMBERSHIP	Associate members Several benefits (discounts and gifts)			
Licenses	https://www.gnu.org/licenses/license-list.html			
FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION EUROPE				
WEB SITE	https://fsfe.org			
ABOUT	A charity that empowers users to control technology			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Executive Council, central teams and local teams			
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations			
MEMBERSHIP	No			
Licenses	https://www.gnu.org/licenses/license-list.html			
FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION INDIA				
WEB SITE	https://fsf.org.in/			
ABOUT	Non-profit organisation committed to advocating, promoting and propagating the use and development of swatantra software in India			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	N
BUSINESS MODEL	Volunteers			
MEMBERSHIP	No			
Licenses	https://www.gnu.org/licenses/license-list.html			
FREE SOFTWARE AND OPEN SOURCE FOUNDATION FOR AFRICA				
WEB SITE	https://fossfa.africa/			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	N
FREE BSD FOUNDATION				

WEB SITE	https://freebsd.foundation.org/			
ABOUT	Non-profit organization dedicated to supporting and promoting the FreeBSD Project and community worldwide			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Partners + individual donors			
MEMBERSHIP	Partnership programme for organizations			
GNOME Foundation				
WEB SITE	https://foundation.gnome.org/			
ABOUT	The GNOME Foundation is a non-profit organization that believes in a world where everyone is empowered by technology they can trust. We do this by building a diverse and sustainable free software personal computing ecosystem			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y GNOME's software is Free Software.
GOVERNANCE MODEL	The GNOME Foundation is comprised of a number of bodies – the Board of Directors, the Executive Director, the Advisory Board, and the GNOME Membership. The <u>GNOME Foundation Charter</u> outlines the overall purpose, structure, and process for the GNOME Foundation. The <u>Bylaws of the GNOME Foundation</u> document the policies and procedures of the Foundation as a non-profit group. The GNOME Foundation also publishes <u>Reports</u> on its activities each year.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Open to all GNOME contributors and every member of the Board of Directors is a contributing member of the GNOME community			
MEMBERSHIP	The Membership consists of all GNOME contributors who wish to become part of the Membership and go through the application process. Members can run for election to the Board of Directors, vote in the elections for the Board of Directors, and suggest referenda. The membership process is overseen by the Membership and Elections Committee			
PROJECTS	One – GNOME 43			
GENTOO FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.gentoo.org/inside-gentoo/foundation/			
ABOUT	The Gentoo Foundation decouples necessary bureaucracy from development, providing faster and higher quality results as the developer can now focus his attention completely at the community and his responsibilities (being software, documentation, infrastructure or others).			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y

GOVERNANCE MODEL	24 companies and organizations are donating various services and equipment to further the development of Gentoo.			
GraphQL FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://foundation.graphql.org/			
ABOUT	The GraphQL Foundation is a neutral foundation founded by global technology and application development companies. It encourages contributions, stewardship, and a shared investment from a broad group in vendor-neutral events, documentation, tools, and support for GraphQL			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	N	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	The GraphQL Foundation encourages contributions, stewardship, and a shared investment from a broad group in vendor-neutral events, documentation, tools, and support for GraphQL.			
MEMBERSHIP	The GraphQL Foundation ensures that the GraphQL community is able to focus on the continued evolution of the specification and reference implementations. They accomplish this through a number of core activities.			
ITPUG (ITALIAN POSTGRESQL USERS' GROUP)				
WEB SITE	https://www.itpug.org/			
ABOUT	ITPUG – Italian PostgreSQL Users Group is a non-profit association for the promotion, dissemination and protection of Free Software (FLOSS) in Italy. In particular, ITPUG promotes the adoption of PostgreSQL, one of the most successful open source projects			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	Y
IDENTITY COMMONS				
WEB SITE	http://idcommons.net/			
ABOUT	Identity Commons supports, facilitates, and promotes the creation of an open identity layer for the Internet, one that maximizes control, convenience, and privacy for the individual while encouraging the development of healthy, interoperable communities			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
INTERNET SYSTEMS CONSORTIUM				
WEB SITE	https://www.isc.org/			
ABOUT	Fostering the development and maintenance of Internet infrastructure and core software for the benefit of the public. Acts as a community information sharing hub, and catalyze community working groups at their semi-annual workshops.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y ISC develops and distributes three open

				source Internet networking software packages: BIND 9, ISC DHCP, and Kea DHCP. BIND 9, ISC's Domain Name System (DNS) software program, is widely used on the Internet by enterprises and service providers, offering a robust and stable platform on top of which organizations can build distributed computing systems.
Licenses	Yes. The MPL 2.0 license (https://opensource.org/license/mpl-2-0/) is approved by the Open Source Initiative.			
KDE e.V				
WEB SITE	https://ev.kde.org/			
ABOUT	KDE e.V. is a registered non-profit organization that represents the KDE Community in legal and financial matters. Read our mission statement.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	KDE e.V. is made up of its members, from which the board of KDE e.V. is elected. The Board of KDE e.V. is responsible for interpreting and adjusting the rules of the program where necessary. KDE e.V. holds its annual general meeting at Academy. During the last AGM, elections for two vacancies on the board of directors were held.			
MEMBERSHIP	<p>Active membership: If you are a member of the KDE community who has contributed to promoting, developing or documenting KDE or doing any other KDE related work, you can join the KDE e.V. as an active member.</p> <p>Supporting membership: If you are a corporation and want to support KDE you can become a supporting member. KDE e.V.'s supporting members provide the material support to carry out KDE e.V.'s activities.</p> <p>Donations: If you want to support KDE by regularly donating money, consider becoming a Supporting Member.</p> <p>Community Partnership Program is meant to provide a formal base for situations where we can collaborate and help one another. It is not meant to</p>			

	replace any other programs of KDE e.V. or the KDE community, including normal or supporting memberships, or other agreements KDE e.V. might do with other organizations or communities. KDE e.V. has a good tradition of supporting developer meetings.			
Licenses	Adopted a Fiduciary Licensing Agreement as the preferred form for assigning copyright to KDE e.V.			
LINUX FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://linuxfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	The Linux Foundation provides a neutral, trusted hub for developers and organizations to code, manage, and scale open technology projects and ecosystems			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors, Advisory Board, Fellows. They aim to democratize code and scale adoption, for all projects. They strive to create new technology categories by identifying trends, accelerating the growth of nascent technologies, and removing barriers to adoption. They help projects streamline operations and boost community engagement with cloud-based, collaborative tooling, contributor and participation analytics, and infrastructure management			
MEMBERSHIP	The Linux Foundation provides members with a platform to better establish themselves as leaders, innovators, and change-makers within the open source community. The members take center stage in driving technology innovation for project ecosystems. Linux Foundation provides membership development to help projects scale fast. Linux Foundation members help support the development of shared technology resources, while accelerating their own innovation through open source leadership and participation in some of the world's most successful open source projects.			
PROJECTS	11 (CloudNative, OpenSSF, OLF Networking, FINOS, Hyperledger Foundation, Automotive Grade Linux, FinOps Foundation, OpenJS Foundation, 3DF, RISC-V, LFEDGE)			
LINUX FUND				
WEB SITE	http://www.linuxfund.org/			
ABOUT	Linux Fund is a community-neutral 501(c)(3) non-profit organization that provides financial and administrative support to the open source community. Their primary focus is to bring <i>promising</i> OSI-compliant software projects to <i>production</i> status and foster the community efforts surrounding them.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
PROJECTS	6 capital projects + 10 projects in the past.			
LINUX PROFESSIONAL INSTITUTE				

WEB SITE	https://www.lpi.org/			
ABOUT	<p>Linux Professional Institute (LPI) is the global certification standard and career support organization for open source professionals. With more than 200,000 certification holders, it's the world's first and largest vendor-neutral Linux and open source certification body. LPI has certified professionals in over 180 countries, delivers exams in multiple languages, and has hundreds of training partners.</p> <p>Their mission is to promote the use of open source by supporting the people who work with it.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	<p>LPI has stakeholders, not shareholders, and focuses on its mission over profit. Their governance model includes a definition of a member which is designed to give our certified open source practitioners a say in the direction of the organization, as well as a number of other benefits.</p> <p>LPI is a member-based organization which encourages public trust while enabling practitioners to influence the direction and appreciation of their profession.</p> <p>LPI's Board of Directors.</p> <p>Directors provide strategic high-level direction and oversight over all facets of LPI's certification, education, membership and other activities.</p>			
MEMBERSHIP	Membership in the Linux Professional Institute (LPI) offers benefits and privileges that will support you, your professional path, and the growth of the open source community.			
Licenses	LPI Certificates			
MOZILLA FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.mozilla.org/foundation/			
ABOUT	<p>The Mozilla Foundation works to ensure the internet remains a public resource that is open and accessible to all. They work toward a healthy internet and trustworthy AI.</p> <p>Mozilla Foundation invests in bold ideas, global leaders, and the convening and campaign power of people. For more than two decades, we've worked across borders, disciplines, and technologies to fuel a movement to realize the full potential of the internet.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
NLnet FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.nlnet.nl/			
ABOUT	<p>NLnet has contributed funding to many important and very visible projects around fundamental standards from securing the core routing protocols and the domain name system of the internet to safer email, vendor-independent videoconferencing, more reliable wireless networks and private instant messaging - all based on open standards and verifiable open source software and/or hardware.</p>			

Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
PROJECTS	There is a long list of projects that they support.			
NLnet FOUNDATION LABS				
WEB SITE	https://www.nlnetlabs.nl			
ABOUT	At the NLnet Labs foundation, they develop software for the benefit of the Internet, enhancing its stability and security			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
PROJECTS	NLnet Labs participates in various research projects which revolve around core Internet infrastructure.			
NetBSD FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.netbsd.org/foundation/			
ABOUT	The NetBSD Foundation serves as the legal entity which owns several of the NetBSD Project servers, handles donations of money, services, hardware or time to the project, and administers NetBSD copyrights.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	The NetBSD Foundation is a non-profit organisation and it is governed by a set of bylaws. It has a Board of Directors. The Board members are elected by the NetBSD Developer community, following the Board election procedure.			
NumFOCUS				
WEB SITE	https://www.numfocus.org/			
ABOUT	The mission of NumFOCUS is to promote open practices in research, data, and scientific computing by serving as a fiscal sponsor for open source projects and organizing community-driven educational programs. It envisions an inclusive scientific and research community that utilizes actively supported open source software to make impactful discoveries for a better world.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
OASIS Open				
WEB SITE	https://oasis-open.org			
ABOUT	OASIS Open is a non-profit standards body; it offers projects—including open source projects—a path to standardization and de jure approval for reference in international policy and procurement. Their mission is to advance the fair, transparent development of open source software and standards through the power of global collaboration and community.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y

MEMBERSHIP	The OASIS membership allows the members to produce high-impact work while making strategic connections.			
PROJECTS	56 projects			
Licenses	Oasis standards, more than 100			
OW2				
WEB SITE	https://www.ow2.org			
ABOUT	OW2 is an independent, global, open-source software community. They foster open source projects and they actually deliver software. The mission of OW2 is to a) promote the development of open-source middleware, generic business applications, cloud computing platforms and b) foster a vibrant community and business ecosystem.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	<p>The OW2 governance is driven by the Bylaws of the OW2 Association.</p> <p>The main bodies implementing the OW2 governance include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the General Assembly <p>The OW2 governance model is designed to comply with the key original founding principles of ObjectWeb: Openness, Fairness, Trust, Transparency, and Independence.</p> <p>Members are given rights in the governance of the organization and the definition of its strategy.</p>			
MEMBERSHIP	<p>Associate Organizations, Individual, Corporate and Strategic Memberships.</p> <p>Members pursue the mission of the Association in the framework of Activities, including Projects and Initiatives, and each activity is driven by a Leader.</p> <p>OW2 Member are welcome to take part in the governance of the Association. In particular, they are entitled to elect the representatives of Corporate Members, or Individual Members depending on your category, on the Board of Directors.</p> <p>New members can easily join, participate in and contribute to one of the on-going.</p>			
PROJECTS	45 projects			
OPEN BIOINFORMATICS FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.open-bio.org			
ABOUT	The Open Bioinformatics Foundation (OBF) is a non-profit, volunteer-run group that promotes open source software development and Open Science within the biological research community.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	The Board established the membership body as the platform from which major future changes to the OBF's mission, agenda, and scope will originate.			

MEMBERSHIP	Membership in the OBF is open to anyone who wants to help promote open source or open science in a biological field. Members are invited to attend public Board meetings, which take place at least once a year.			
PROJECTS	16 projects			
OPEN HARDWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://wiki.p2pfoundation.net/Open_Hardware_Foundation			
ABOUT	The OHF is a non-profit corporation whose stated goals are to facilitate the design, development, and production of free and open hardware.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
BUSINESS MODEL	Collaboration with Traversal to produce cards, pooling resources			
OPEN INFRASTRUCTURE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://openinfra.dev/about/			
ABOUT	Helping to establish new open source communities to advance areas where technology can successfully contribute to the development of open infrastructure: AI/Machine Learning, CI/CD, Container Infrastructure, Edge Computing and of course, Public, Private and Hybrid Clouds.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	27 member board of directors, 15-20 staff members			
MEMBERSHIP	110K in 187 countries			
PROJECTS	Eight, including OpenStack			
OPEN SOURCE COLLECTIVE				
WEB SITE	https://www.oscollective.org/			
ABOUT	The Open Source Collective is a non-profit umbrella organisation providing financial and legal infrastructure for thousands of open source projects – an “API” between the world of distributed collaboration and the world of accounting and invoices.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Staff of approximately 15 people listed. There is a Board.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Coordinates with sponsor companies to comply with their purchase order process and invoicing requirements. Fees are 10% of incoming funds, plus payment processor fees.			
PROJECTS	Not known but could be several hundred sponsored.			
Licenses	Manages a list of all OSS licenses and helps membership to understand best ones for them.			
OPEN SOURCE GEOSPATIAL				
WEB SITE	https://www.osgeo.org/			

ABOUT	The Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGeo) is a not-for-profit organization whose mission is to foster global adoption of open geospatial technology by being an inclusive software foundation devoted to an open philosophy and participatory community driven development.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	OSGeo charter members elect a 9 member board of directors who appoint officers and work together set the vision and goals for the foundation. The board empowers a set of committees and volunteers to execute on these goals.			
BUSINESS MODEL	There are sponsors donating, and events are also sponsored.			
MEMBERSHIP	Unknown but seems substantial. Many outreach committees including marketing, conference, incubation committees. There are local, regional, and country-wide chapters. These chapters support advocacy activities.			
PROJECTS	Approx. 80			
OPEN SOURCE INITIATIVE				
WEB SITE	https://opensource.org/			
ABOUT	The Open Source Initiative (OSI) is a non-profit corporation with global scope formed to educate about and advocate for the benefits of open source and to build bridges among different constituencies in the open source community.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Eleven board members.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Membership-based, with an Affiliate Membership program, plus Corporate Sponsors. Membership is fee-based.			
MEMBERSHIP	Not known, but certainly substantial. There is an active community that promotes membership.			
PROJECTS	It is only advocacy, not projects			
Licenses	The OSI has a very thorough set of resources to explain the differed OSS license types.			
OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE INSTITUTE				
WEB SITE	https://www.ossinstitute.org/			
ABOUT	The mission of the OSSI is to provide (1) An accurate, dynamic map of available resources and programs in the open source space, and (2) Accessible guidance from vendor-neutral, technology agnostic experts			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Non-profit based in California			
BUSINESS MODEL	Government personnel can join free of charge. Individual membership is \$80/year. Business Sponsorship is solicited.			

MEMBERSHIP	Membership development activities include short weekly podcasts; a blog to answer questions about OSS; vendor-neutral mentoring on Licensing, Integration, Security, and Support; invitations to local and virtual technical events; direct access to OSS experts.			
OpenBSD FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.openbsdoundation.org/			
ABOUT	To support and further the development, advancement, and maintenance of free software based on the OpenBSD operating system, including the operating system itself and related free software projects			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Solicits contributions both from individuals and Companies.			
MEMBERSHIP	Not seeking new members at this time.			
PROJECTS	Funds improvements to the OpenBSD system			
OpenID Foundation				
WEB SITE	https://openjsf.org/			
ABOUT	The OpenID Foundation is a non-profit international standardization organization of individuals and companies committed to enabling, promoting and protecting OpenID technologies.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	10 member board, 14 member cross-project council, 4 staff			
BUSINESS MODEL	F Fee-based membership, paid Certification, also manage IP, significant corporate membership			
MEMBERSHIP	Ten working groups for members to interact, discounted fees for certification, etc., local chapters			
PROJECTS	Currently about 32, all concerning JavaScript			
OpenJSF FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://openjsf.org/			
ABOUT	The OpenJS Foundation is the premier home for critical open source JavaScript projects			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	10 member board, 14 member cross-project council, 4 staff			
BUSINESS MODEL	Fee based membership individual up to Platinum corporate			
MEMBERSHIP	Services to members like a Java Script Landia program for info on JS news, plus discounts on other services			

PROJECTS	Currently about 32, all concerning JavaScript			
OpenSourceMatters				
WEB SITE	https://www.opensourcematters.org/			
ABOUT	Non-profit organisation supporting the Joomla! project			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors is comprised of 3 Department Coordination Team Leaders + 4 Officers required by law			
BUSINESS MODEL	All volunteer organisations			
MEMBERSHIP	Around 200 globally (recall that this is for a single project) Dedicated outreach department, several volunteer teams for various development and test activities for Joomla!			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	Appears to be around 200			
OpenStreetMap Foundation				
WEB SITE	https://wiki.osmfoundation.org/wiki/Main_Page			
ABOUT	Initiative to create and provide free geographic data, such as street maps, to anyone. Specific relevance to the OpenStreetMap project.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	10 member board of directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Small yearly fee for individuals; free for contributors. Corporate membership up to Platinum.			
MEMBERSHIP	Provide services to members such as info on getting access to OpenStreetMap data, making Data Processing Agreements, GPX APIs, blog, working groups, etc.			
PROJECTS	Essentially only one			
OpenUK				
WEB SITE	https://openuk.uk/			
ABOUT	Purpose is to develop UK leadership and global collaboration in open technology			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	15 member board, 24 member “leadership committee”			
BUSINESS MODEL	Activities paid for by Donors and Sponsors			
MEMBERSHIP	Unclear, but likely to be significant – this is a major organization Many events sponsored; an “Ambassadors” program offering benefits to members, Open Kids Camp, Honors List, etc.			
Oregon State University Open Source Lab Alliance				
WEB SITE	https://osuosl.org/			

ABOUT	Non-profit organization working for the advancement of open source technologies			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Staff of about 5 persons, let by a Director			
BUSINESS MODEL	Small funding from the University, but mostly external donations. Annual expenses approximately \$400K			
MEMBERSHIP	There is no “membership” or community as such, only the services provided to the OSS community at large.			
PROJECTS	Approximately 160			
PARTICIPATORY CULTURE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://pculture.org/			
ABOUT	Dedicated to creating technologies, services, and communities that ensure a more collaborative, inclusive world.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	22 Member team, board of directors, advisory board			
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations solicited. Major funders include the EC, Mellon Foundation, Mozilla. Services also offered for their projects (e.g., Amara subtitle)			
PROJECTS	Three: Amara, Miro Video player, Miro video converter			
PLONE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://plone.org/foundation			
ABOUT	Non-profit organization that exists to protect and promote Plone (a FOSS content management system built on top of the Zope application server)			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Seven member Board, plus auxiliary structures such as a Steering Circle and Open Organizational Discussions			
BUSINESS MODEL	100% funded by sponsorships			
MEMBERSHIP	Approx. 125 current members “Ambassadors” initiative.			
PROJECTS	Essentially only one: Plone			
PostgreSQL Brasil / Curitiba				
WEB SITE	https://www.meetup.com/PostgreSQL-Curitiba			
ABOUT	Promotion of PostgreSQL in Brazil.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	Y

MEMBERSHIP	519 members Local events			
PostgreSQL Europe				
WEB SITE	https://postgresql.eu/			
ABOUT	"n "umbrella gr"up" for all PostgreSQL user groups in Europe.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	5 member Board of Directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Small bi-annual membership fee			
MEMBERSHIP	Coordination of events including event management software			
PROJECTS	Only PostgreSQL			
PostgreSQL US				
WEB SITE	https://postgresql.us/			
ABOUT	Purpose is to support the growth and education of PostgreSQL			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	5 member board, 4 officers, non-profit public charity			
BUSINESS MODEL	Annual membership fee (normal and student). Donations and sponsors			
MEMBERSHIP	Special privileges and access to resources for members			
PROJECTS	Only PostgrSQL			
PostgreSQL FR				
WEB SITE	https://www.postgresql.fr//asso:accueil			
ABOUT	Promotes the PostgreSQL database management system in French-speaking countries.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	9 member board, annual general assembly			
BUSINESS MODEL	Corporate membership 400 Euros per year. Active seeking of sponsors.			
MEMBERSHIP	"several dozen" Conferences, a PGDay, assistance to users, translations of documents, etc.			
PROJECTS	Only PostgrSQL			
PYTHON SOFTWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.python.org/ https://www.python.org/psf-landing/			
ABOUT	The Python Software Foundation is an organization devoted to advancing open source technology related to the Python programming language.			

Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors and Officers			
BUSINESS MODEL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sponsorship 			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grants 			
PROJECTS	Support and maintain python.org, The Python Package Index, Python Documentation			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	More than 100			
SOFTWARE FREEDOM CONSERVANCY				
WEB SITE	https://sfconservancy.org/			
ABOUT	Software Freedom Conservancy is a non-profit organization centered around ethical technology. Our mission is to ensure the right to repair, improve and reinstall software. We promote and defend these rights through fostering free and open source software (FOSS) projects, driving initiatives that actively make technology more inclusive, and advancing policy strategies that defend FOSS (such as copyleft).			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Sponsors and Sustainers			
MEMBERSHIP	Members			
PROJECTS	54 current			
SOFTWARE FREEDOM LAW CENTER				
WEB SITE	https://www.softwarefreedom.org/			
ABOUT	Software Freedom Law Center's practice brings together expertise in all the fields of law that FOSS projects are affected by, including copyrights, patents, trademarks, and non-profit governance.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Directors and Staff			
BUSINESS MODEL	Services for a fee			

PROJECTS	Not indicated			
SOFTWARE IN THE PUBLIC INTEREST				
WEB SITE	https://www.spi-inc.org/			
ABOUT	Software in the Public Interest (SPI) is a non-profit corporation registered in the state of New York founded to act as a fiscal sponsor for organizations that develop open source software and hardware. Our mission is to help substantial and significant open source projects by handling their non-technical administrative tasks so that they a'en't required to operate their own legal entity.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Sponsors			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Sponsorship 			
PROJECTS	40 projects			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	243			
SUBVERSION CORPORATION				
WEB SITE	https://subversion.apache.org/			
ABOUT	Subversion exists to be universally recognized and adopted as an open-source, centralized version control system characterized by its reliability as a safe haven for valuable data; the simplicity of its model and usage; and its ability to support the needs of a wide variety of users and projects, from individuals to large-scale enterprise operations.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
TYPO3 ASSOCIATION				
WEB SITE	https://typo3.org/project/association/			
ABOUT	The TYPO3 Association builds the groundwork for the TYPO3 project. We empower our community with infrastructure and guidance. Our decisions are long term oriented.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	The income from memberships, donations and events is essential to the TYPO3 project. We funnel approximately €650,000 back into core development and community projects every year.			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Member: €7.92 • Bronze (Freelancers): € 100 once + € 125 / year • Silver (Small Business): € 500 once + € 1.000 / year • Gold (Professional): € 500 once + € 2.750/year 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platinum (Enterprise): € 500 once + € 12.500/year Academic : Price not specified <p>The income from memberships, donations and events is essential to the TYPO3 project. We funnel approximately €650,000 back into core development and community projects every year.</p>			
TeX USERS GROUP				
WEB SITE	https://tug.org/			
ABOUT	The TeX Users Group (TUG) is a membership-based not-for-profit organization, founded in 1980, for anyone who uses the TeX typesetting system created by Donald Knuth and/or is interested in typography and font design.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	TeX Users Group Board of Directors			
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations and Membership Fees			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TUG Members and Institutional Members Funding of Projects 			
PERL FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.perlfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	The Perl Foundation is dedicated to the advancement of the PERL and RAKU programming languages through open discussion, collaboration, design and code.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board Members and Advisory Board Members			
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations and Sponsors			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donors and Sponsors support grants for projects Grants, support 			
TWISTED SOFTWARE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://github.com/twisted/trac-wiki-archive/blob/trunk/TwistedSoftwareFoundation.mediawiki			
ABOUT	Absorbed by the Software Freedom Conservancy			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	N	Y
WIKIMEDIA FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://wikimediafoundation.org/			
ABOUT	The non-profit Wikimedia Foundation provides the essential infrastructure for free knowledge. We host Wikipedia, the free online encyclopaedia, created, edited, and verified by volunteers around the world, as well as many other vital			

	community projects. All of which is made possible thanks to donations from individuals like you. We welcome anyone who shares our vision to join us in collecting and sharing knowledge that fully represents human diversity.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations			
MEMBERSHIP	No Members, but a massive number of contributors			
PROJECTS	90+ million media files			
WORDPRESS FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://wordpressfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	The point of the foundation is to ensure free access, in perpetuity, to the software projects we support. People and businesses may come and go, so it is important to ensure that the source code for these projects will survive beyond the current contributor base, that we may create a stable platform for web publishing for generations to come . As part of this mission, the Foundation will be responsible for protecting the WordPress, WordCamp, and related trademarks. A 501(c)3 non-profit organization, the WordPress Foundation pursues a charter to educate the public about WordPress and related open source software.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	<p>Sustainer – \$1000 per year</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> René Hermenau / WP Staging 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ and 7 Anonymous Donors Supporter – \$ 50 per year ☐ Andrew Norcross ☐ Danny Santoro ☐ Dan Soschin ☐ Donna Cavalier ☐ James Huff ☐ Jamieson Webking ☐ Ken Gagne ☐ M Asif Rahman ☐ Max Foster ☐ Peer Dicken ☐ Ryan Meghdies ☐ Sé Reed ☐ WPMangeNinja LLC ☐ and 16 Anonymous Donors Giver – \$ 10 per year ☐ Attorney Saim İncekaş ☐ Ben Greeley ☐ Fahim Murshed ☐ Finest Web Geek ☐ Herman Asrori ☐ Mainul Kabir Aion ☐ McCullough Web Services ☐ Michael Adegoke ☐ Morgan Estes ☐ Nomad Skateboarding ☐ Tomoki Oi ☐ Vitalii Rudnykh ☐ Wasim S. ☐ and 71 Anonymous Donors 			
MEMBERSHIP	231,870 members			
X.ORG FOUNDATION LLC				
WEB SITE	https://www.x.org/wiki/XorgFoundation/			
ABOUT	<p>X.Org Foundat'on's (or X.Org for short) purpose is to research, develop, support, organize, administrate, standardize, promote, and defend a free and open accelerated graphics stack and the developers and users thereof. This stack includes, but is not limited to, the following projects: DRM, Mesa, Wayland and the X Window System.</p> <p>The X.Org Foundation has an open membership, and a Board of Directors which is elected from the membership. Please check the Board Of Directors page for information about the Board. Information on how to join the X.Org Foundation can be found on the Membership page.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of Directors: https://www.x.org/wiki/BoardOfDirectors/			

BUSINESS MODEL	Sponsorship and Donations: https://www.x.org/wiki/SponsorshipPage/			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Membership: https://www.x.org/wiki/Membership/ Events :https://www.x.org/wiki/Events/ Reimbursement for Member Travel and Expenses: https://www.x.org/wiki/XorgFoundation/Policies/Reimbursement/ 			
XMPP STANDARDS FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://xmpp.org/about/xmpp-standards-foundation.html			
ABOUT	<p>The XMPP Standards Foundation (also known as the XSF and formerly the Jabber Software Foundation) is an independent, non-profit standards development organisation whose primary mission is to define open protocols for presence, instant messaging, and real-time communication and collaboration on top of the IETF's Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP).</p> <p>The XSF also provides information and infrastructure to the worldwide community of Jabber/XMPP developers, service providers, and end users.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board: https://xmpp.org/about/xmpp-standards-foundation/			
BUSINESS MODEL	Sponsorship			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Membership: https://xmpp.org/community/membership/ Members: https://xmpp.org/about/xsf/members/ Events: https://xmpp.org/community/events/ 			
XIPH FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://xiph.org/			
ABOUT	<p>The Xiph.Org Foundation is a non-profit corporation dedicated to protecting the foundations of Internet multimedia from control by private interests. Our purpose is to support and develop free, open protocols and software to serve the public, developer and business markets.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	Donations : https://xiph.org/donate/			
MEMBERSHIP	Open membership			
PROJECTS	23 projects listed			

2.2 First Level Data Analysis

As part of the process of analysing the existing open source organisations, we used the found database (<https://som-research.github.io/OSSFFoundations/#/>) and found 106 open source organisations that had been identified by researchers.

It is important to note that of the 106 organisations, 37 were either determined to be out of scope for SWForum or were no longer active (35% of those analysed).

Of the relevant organisations, 83% were of an international scope and more than 89% were considered to be independent, with 59% being considered fully transparent in their activities.

58% of the organisations are supporting software products or are technology dependent.

45% of the analysed organisations have a Governance Model with a Board of Directors (or Governing Board, Executive Council, Board of Trustees, Advisory Board or Other) – note that this information was not always available for each organisation however.

Initial first analysis shows that the existing sustainable organisations had a mix of the following:

- 1) Multiple funding sources (membership, sponsorship, donations, licensing, projects)
- 2) Membership development activities
- 3) Broad set of membership, and
- 4) Ability to adapt to the software development environment

2.3 Clustering of the Open Source Organisations

Of the 106 Open Source foundations identified in the database (<https://som-research.github.io/OSSFFoundations/#/>), 69 were determined to be “in scope” and relevant for SWForum.

In order to better understand the Landscape of Open Source organisations relevant for what SWForum is trying to achieve, we have taken the Open Source organisations and clustered them according to a number of criteria determined to be important. These clusters are thus framed in the following categories:

- 1) International (57 orgs) or Regional Scope (12 orgs)
- 2) Product / Framework / and/or Technology Dependent (40 orgs)
- 3) Generic Operating Systems (OS) – (24 orgs)
- 4) SWForum Pillars:
 - a. Digital Infrastructures (2 orgs)
 - b. Operating Systems (10 orgs)
 - c. Software Technologies (22 orgs)
 - d. Special Application Domains (20 orgs)
- 5) Focused Upon Specific Licenses (27 orgs)

A brief explanation of the cluster categories follows.

The International or Regional Scope is self-explanatory and it is very clear that there are many more organisations with an International focus.

Organisations that are Product, Framework and/or Technology Dependent are often subject to the changing evolution of the software development landscape and what is being currently used and as such are subject to becoming quickly outmoded when there is an innovation or a change in the tools and methods concerning software development.

Organisations based upon a Generic Operating system have a clear focus and in some ways are the “promoters” of their own success. The more users and developers that an operating system has, the better chance it has for longer term “take up” and success.

The next four clusters are representative of the **4 SWForum pillars** and as such are highly relevant for SWForum.

Digital Infrastructures represent an important cluster, however, few of the open source organisations fall into this category as most of the digital infrastructure world is a “for profit” and even “proprietary” in this respect.

Operating Systems focused organisations are key in the open source community as operating systems form the core and basis of software development and are the base on which everything is built.

Software Technologies are “part and parcel” of the development of software and also represent a key ingredient in the open source environment.

And finally, there are many **Special Application Domains** which are represented by these open source organisations identified and as such, the organisations provide the basis for continuing significant support in the specific applications domains.

The last cluster (and definitely not the “least”) is those organisations that are **Focused Upon Specific Licenses**. The importance of this cluster represents one of the key sustainability models in that licenses can be provided via a payment or via attribution and using the license name – both of these approaches provide elements of a sustainable business model, such that this cluster is important for the long-term concept.

It is also important to note that an organisation can be part of multiple clusters – for example, the Eclipse Foundation organisation is part of 4 clusters (international scope, product/framework/technology dependent, software technologies, and focus on specific licenses clusters). And this is possibility for a number of the organisations studied.

The following charts show the clustering with respect to the entities relevant for SWForum: This Landscape Report deliverable is the second in a series of two Reports, meant to describe the landscape surrounding the SWForum and the current existing and successful structures, which can provide model elements for the final form of the SWForum.

Figure 1: International Scope Cluster (57 organisations identified)

It is important to note the 83% of the organisations identified as relevant fall into the cluster of international scope – making this one of the key parameters.

Figure 2: Regional Scope Cluster (12 organisations identified)

The Regional Scope Cluster represents approximately 17% of the organisations identified and it is noted at the same time that Regional Scope can also be quite relevant.

Figure 3: – Product/ Framework/ Technology Dependent Cluster (40 organisations identified)

With 58% of the relevant organisations identified falling in the Product / Framework / Technology Dependent Cluster it is clear that this is one of the most important characteristics of the existing and successful open source organisations.

Figure 4: Generic Operating System Cluster (24 organisations identified)

Generic Operating Systems (OS) Cluster represents about 35% of the organisations studied and thus is another important sector addressed by the Open Source foundations.

CLUSTERS ACCORDING TO THE SWFORUM PILLARS FOLLOW:

Figure 5: Digital Infrastructure Cluster (2 organisations identified)

Figure 6: Operating Systems Cluster (10 organisations identified)

Figure 7: Software Technologies Cluster (22 organisations identified)

Figure 8: Special Application Domain (20 organisations identified)

Figure 9: Focus on Specific Licenses Cluster (27 organisations identified)

The following chart (Fig. 10) shows the percentage of organisations identified for each of the clusters (note: this totals more than 100% as organisations can appear in multiple clusters, 2nd note: Digital Infrastructures represents only 2.9% of the organisations).

Figure 10: Percentage of organisations identified for each of the clusters

2.4 Initial findings of the Clustering Exercise

The top 3 clusters are International Scope, Product/Framework/Technology Dependent, and Focused on Specific Licenses.

The number of organisations that are classified by the number of clusters:

- ▣ Number of organisations identified as belonging in 5 clusters = 5 (4.35%)
- ▣ Number of organisations identified as belonging in 4 clusters = 19 (27.54%)
- ▣ Number of organisations identified as belonging in 3 clusters = 30 (43.48%)
- ▣ Number of organisations identified as belonging in 2 clusters = 16 (21.29%)
- ▣ Number of organisations identified as belonging in 1 cluster = 1 (1.45%)
- ▣ This distribution follows almost exactly a “bell curve” structure.

The organisations that are belonging to 5 clusters are actually in the exact same 5 clusters in fact. These 5 common clusters are:

- ▣ International Scope
- ▣ Product / Framework / Technology Dependent
- ▣ Generic OS
- ▣ Operating Systems
- ▣ Focus on Specific Licenses

With this clustering exercise it becomes clear that specific connections to software, products, licensing and frameworks are often key in ensuring sustainability. Furthermore, there is also a certain scale factor which is relevant, considering the number of users (developers) involved and the spread and user “take up” of the software, technology or framework. Further final and overall conclusions can be found in the last section of this deliverable.

3 Conclusions and lessons learnt

3.1 The important role of foundations

A large number of the entities identified in the Landscape Report are open source foundations. They play a particularly important role in the open source community, and for achieving many of Europe's goals such as digital sovereignty.

Plurality is one of the biggest strengths in OSS. Too often, it has been said, "Just leave it to the market to resolve the issues." But this too often has led to gaps (cf. medical care, for example). This is where foundations can play a part. As neutral actors, they can help to disseminate experience in cybersecurity, awareness, education. They can be aware of the pain points and direct funding there, not favouring specific companies, etc.

Work at the foundations may well be neutral, but the results do filter back to the business community. For example, at the Apache foundation, contributors are volunteers with respect to Apache, but are employees of beneficiary organisations and can bring back the results to their companies.

The foundations also perform important analyses of pending legislation and its effects on their constituencies. One example is the proposed Cybersecurity Resilience Act (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/cyber-resilience-act>). The foundations are important in the discussion of OSS security. At the Eclipse Foundation, a case study of a company was created to show the effects of the proposed legislation; even more such case studies should be created, so that people can see what really happens to companies when the legislation takes effect.

Foundations can also provide support to remedy gaps and deficiencies in the current ecosystem. Consider, for example, the problem of source code. Source code is one type of data, whose importance is too often overlooked (many problems in the past came from the non-availability of source code of components). Currently, many holders of source code are outside Europe and for-profit. What if they decide to stop making available? The Software Heritage Foundation represents a European source of software source code. Access to vulnerability information (e.g., CVE databases) is another type of critical data. Here again, most of it is curated by non-European entities. Another task is for Europe to have an independent channel to such vulnerability information, which may be possible through an appropriate foundation.

Foundations can also serve to help introduce open source into sectors that previously paid little or no attention to it. For example, one of the foundations listed in this Landscape Report is the Fintech Open Source Foundation. When PSD2 (creating an open banking ecosystem) was introduced in 2018, the banks were upset, but it has indeed had positive effects and opened up the fintech sector. European fintech has actually grown faster than American fintech since then. Banks are now incorporating more and more open source, and are contributing to the foundation.

3.2 The growing importance of the Open Source Programme Office

There has been a significant growth of European OSPOs (*Open Source Programme Offices*) both in public sector and in industry. The development of OSPOs throughout European governments has been key: it grants a form of "permission" to industry in the sense that companies see the government involved in OSS. The most prominent example is the EC Open Source Programme Office. But there are more and more programmes launching all the time, including:

- 📄 The UK Government Digital Service (GDS) Open Source Team - <https://technology.blog.gov.uk/category/open-source/>
- 📄 The French Government's Direction Interministérielle du Numérique et du Système d'Information et de Communication de l'État (DINSIC) - <https://www.numerique.gouv.fr>
- 📄 The Dutch Government's Open Government Programme - <https://www.opengovpartnership.org/members/netherlands/>
- 📄 The Italian Digital Transformation Team's Open Source Observatory and Repository - <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/open-source-observatory-osor/news/italy-creates-digital-transfo>
- 📄 The Norwegian Government Agency for Public Management and eGovernment's (Difi) Open Source Program Office - <https://www.digdir.no/>

Equally important are the OSPOs being established within European companies, to promote the use, production, and contribution of OSS within the commercial ecosystems within which the companies participate. Some examples include:

- 📄 Red Hat Open Source Program Office
- 📄 SUSE Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Nokia Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Bosch Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Siemens Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Ericsson Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Volvo Group Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Deutsche Bank Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Thales Group Open Source Program Office
- 📄 Deutsche Telekom Open Source Program Office

Note that these come from all different types of domains, ranging from mission-critical (e.g., Bosch automotive, Thales) to financial, to telecom.

3.3 Open source organisations considered to be the most successful and sustainable

There are several open-source software foundations that are widely recognized for their success in supporting and promoting open-source software development:

1. The Apache Software Foundation (ASF): The ASF is a non-profit organization that provides support and governance for over 350 open-source software projects. These projects include popular tools like Apache Hadoop, Apache Spark, and Apache Kafka. The ASF is known for its strong community focus and its commitment to open governance.
2. The Linux Foundation: The Linux Foundation is a non-profit organization that supports the development of the Linux operating system and other open-source projects. It provides a range of services, including training and certification programs, legal and licensing support, and community events. The Linux Foundation is particularly known for its work in supporting the growth and adoption of the Linux ecosystem.
3. The Eclipse Foundation: The Eclipse Foundation is a non-profit organization that provides a platform for open-source software development. It supports a range of projects, including the Eclipse IDE, which is widely used by software developers. The Eclipse Foundation is known for its focus on building an open, collaborative community of developers and its commitment to high-quality software development practices.

4. The Mozilla Foundation: The Mozilla Foundation is a non-profit organization that supports the development of open-source software and technologies that promote a free and open internet. It is perhaps best known for its work on the Firefox web browser, which is built using open-source technologies.
5. The Free Software Foundation (FSF): The FSF is a non-profit organization that advocates for the use and development of free software. It is the home of the GNU project, which has developed a range of free software tools, including the GNU Compiler Collection (GCC) and the GNU Debugger (GDB). The FSF is known for its advocacy work, including its efforts to promote the use of free software in education and government.

These are just a few examples of the most successful and sustainable open-source software organisations. Each of these organisations plays an important role in supporting and promoting open-source software development and helping to build vibrant, collaborative communities of developers around the world.

OpenForum Europe (OFE) is a not-for-profit, Brussels-based independent think tank which explains the merits of openness in computing to policy makers and communities across Europe. However, this was not included in the analysis as it is not an open source developers organisation and as a not-for-profit, European-based independent think tank, it focuses on openness within the ICT sector, OFE draws its support from a variety of partners and supporters: global industry players, European SMEs and consumer organisations, as well as the open community.

3.4 Overall conclusions

The most successful and sustainable open source organisations are those linked with a product / framework / technology and those that offer some licensing service to the community. Moreover, the evolution of open software development and how it is used has a significant effect on the sustainability of the organisation involved: many times there are important innovations and changes which affect the relevance of the organisations implicated. While it is hard to quantify the ability to adapt to the ever-evolving software development environment, the most successful and sustainable organisations appear to be the ones that are always adapting and evolving their approach and their “offering” to their members and their stakeholders. As mentioned previously, the number of users (developers) involved and the penetration of the software, product, service or framework has a significant effect on sustainability. Finally, open source organisations’ business models can vary significantly from licensing, to fee for service, or even just simple membership fees, with the licensing being one of the more important aspects in ensuring potential longer term stability.

The open source organisations widely considered to be the 5 most successful, as mentioned previously, are:

- 1) Apache Software Foundation (ASF)
- 2) The Linux Foundation
- 3) The Eclipse Foundation
- 4) The Mozilla Foundation
- 5) The Free Software Foundation (FSF)

These organisations can be used as models, although they all operate in different ways. Of these five, four are associated with a specific software product or framework and the fifth is focused upon advocating for the use and development of free software. Licensing is part of four as focused on software products and framework, while the Free Software Foundation has a business model of memberships, sponsorship and external support.

Inevitably, organisations need a sustainable business model which includes a financial component either offered by its members, by licensing or by sponsorship and external support.

REFERENCES

WEBSITE REFERENCES FOR THE SOURCE DATA:

Note: Those organizations highlighted in orange are either out of scope or no longer active.

https://som-research.github.io/OSSFfoundations/#/
https://dotnetfoundation.org/
https://adainitiative.org/
https://www.apache.org/foundation/
http://associacao.softwarelivre.org/
https://bsdfund.org/
https://benetech.org/
https://biobricks.org/
http://www.blender.org/blenderorg/blender-foundation/
https://www.techcultivation.org/
https://www.cloudfoundry.org/foundation/
https://creativecommons.org/
https://www.digitalfreedomfoundation.org/
http://dff.org.in/
https://www.djangoproject.com/foundation/
https://www.documentfoundation.org/
https://www.eclipse.org/org/foundation/
https://csol.org/
https://www.eff.org/
https://foundation.fsharp.org/
https://www.finos.org/
http://freeknowledge.eu/
http://www.fsf.org/
https://fsfe.org
http://fsf.org.in/

http://www.fsfla.org/
https://fossfa.africa/
https://freebsd.foundation.org/
https://www.vialibre.org.ar/en/home/
https://foundation.gnome.org/
https://www.gentoo.org/inside-gentoo/foundation/
https://foundation.graphql.org/
https://www.itpug.org/
https://www.idcommons.org/
https://www.isc.org/
https://www.postgresql.jp/
https://ev.kde.org/
https://kuali.org
https://www.socallinuxexpo.org/scale/20x
http://linuxfoundation.org/
http://www.linuxfund.org/
http://www.li.org/
https://www.lpi.org/
http://foundation.logilogs.org/
https://www.mamboserver.com/
https://foundation.mozilla.org/en/
https://nlnet.nl/
https://www.nlnetlabs.nl/
https://www.netbsd.org/foundation/
https://numfocus.org/
https://www.oasis-open.org/
https://www.oseinstitute.org/
https://www.ow2.org/
http://www.laptop.org/

https://www.open-bio.org
https://www.opencompute.org/
https://www.oeconsortium.org/about-oecon/
https://wiki.p2pfoundation.net/Open_Hardware_Foundation
https://www.openhealthtools.org/
https://openinfra.dev/about/
Not available
http://www.osafoundation.org/
https://www.oscollective.org/
http://opensourceforamerica.org/about-osfa/our-mission/
https://www.osgeo.org/content/foundation/about.html
https://opensource.org/
https://ossinstitute.org/
https://www.openbsd.foundation.org/
http://www.opendocsociety.org/
https://openid.net/foundation/
https://openjsf.org/
https://www.opensourcematters.org/
https://wiki.osmfoundation.org/wiki/Main_Page
https://openuk.uk/
https://osuosl.org/
http://www.parrot.org/foundation/
http://pculture.org/
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Freenode#Peer-Directed_Projects_Center
https://plone.org/foundation
http://postgresql.org.br
https://www.postgresql.eu/
https://postgresql.us/

https://www.postgresql.fr//asso:accueil
http://www.pubsoft.org/
https://www.python.org/psf-landing/
https://sahanafoundation.org/
https://www.shuttleworthfoundation.org/
https://sfconservancy.org/
https://softwarefreedom.org/
http://solarargentina.org/
http://www.softwarelibrechile.cl/
http://www.softwarelivre.org/
https://www.spi-inc.org/
https://subversion.apache.org/
https://typo3.org/project/association/
https://tug.org/
http://theopenplanningproject.org/
https://perlfoundation.org/
http://www.tsc.org/
https://github.com/twisted/trac-wiki-archive/blob/trunk/TwistedSoftwareFoundation.mediawiki
https://www.wikimediafoundation.org
https://wikipototics.org/en/Wikipototics_Foundation
https://wordpressfoundation.org
https://www.x.org/wiki/XorgFoundation
https://xmpp.org/about/xmpp-standards-foundation.html
https://xiph.org/
http://foundation.zope.org/

ANNEX 1: Organizations “Out of scope” or no longer in existence

Out of Scope

Table 2: Organizations “Out of scope”

ADA Initiative				
WEB SITE	https://adainitiative.org/			
ABOUT	A former not-for-profit which supported women in open technology and culture (2011-2015)			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	2 Co-founders			
BUSINESS MODEL	Volunteer basis			
MEMBERSHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Volunteers and memberships (no specific policy) <input type="checkbox"/> Sponsorship or partnership were accepted if they contributed to the mission of increasing the status and participation of women in open technology and culture 			
PROJECTS	Not applicable (they offer mainly training material)			
Licenses	Creative Commons mainly (OUT OF SCOPE)			
BIOBRICKS FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://biobricks.org/ (out of scope)			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
CREATIVE COMMONS				
WEB SITE	https://creativecommons.org/			
ABOUT	Creative Commons is a non-profit organization that helps overcome legal obstacles to the sharing of knowledge and creativity Out of scope (nothing to do with OSS)			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
DIGITAL FREEDOM FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://www.digitalfreedomfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	Out of scope (nothing to do with OSS)			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	N	N
DIGITAL FREEDOM FOUNDATION INDIA				
WEB SITE	http://dff.org.in/			
ABOUT	Out of scope (nothing to do with OSS)			

Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	N
EL CENTRO DE SOFTWARE LIBRE				
WEB SITE	http://www.csol.org/			
ABOUT	[Out of scope]			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	N
ELECTRONIC FRONTIER FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://www.eff.org/			
ABOUT	[Out of scope]			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
FUNDACION VIA LIBRE				
WEB SITE	https://www.vialibre.org.ar/en/home/			
ABOUT	Out of scope			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	N
JPUG (JAPANESE PostgreSQL USERS' GROUP)				
WEB SITE	https://www.postgresql.jp/			
ABOUT	This group holds a conference every year. The next conference will be held at AP Nihonbashi in Tokyo on Friday, November 11, 2022. Japan website of PostgreSQL User Association (JPUG). PostgreSQL Japanese translation manual, links to PostgreSQL downloads, various event			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	N/A			
BUSINESS MODEL	N/A			
MEMBERSHIP	N/A			
KUALI FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://kuali.org			
ABOUT	Kuali is an organization dedicated to providing software to higher education that allows institutions to lower costs and achieve operational control through open source collaboration, including the option to run it in the cloud, reducing on-premise costs. Their comprehensive suite has been specifically designed by college and university partners to meet their own needs.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y

GOVERNANCE MODEL	The Kuali Foundation’s Board of Directors oversees the health and growth of the Foundation and its projects. In addition, the Board defines the Kuali brand.			
MEMBERSHIP	Membership in the Kuali Foundation affords an institution the ability to be a design partner and to have decision rights about future vision and priorities for the product. The Foundation provides its Members the frameworks for collaboration and governance on the software projects, and facilitates best practices.			
PROJECTS	Two projects: Kuali Research - Simplified Grant Administration			
LINUX EXPO OF SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA				
WEB SITE	https://www.socallinuxexpo.org/scale/20x			
LINUX INTERNATIONAL				
WEB SITE	http://www.li.org/			
ABOUT	Linux International, is an international, non-profit association of users that work towards the international understanding and use of Free and Open Source Software.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	N	Y
LOGILOGI FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://foundation.logilogi.org/			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
MAMBO FOUNDATION INC.				
WEB SITE	https://www.mamboserver.com/			
ABOUT	The goal of MamboServer is to provide an unbiased look at the web hosting industries and the companies operating within it. They have hands-on experience with all the major hosting providers on the market and use their extensive knowledge to create informative and helpful content for their readers. They perform Web hosting comparisons.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	N	Y	Y
OPEN COMPUTE PROJECT				
WEB SITE	https://www.opencompute.org/			
ABOUT	The Open Compute Project Foundation (OCP) was initiated in 2011 with a mission to apply the benefits of open source and open collaboration to hardware and rapidly increase the pace of innovation in, near and around the data center.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	7 Board members, 14 Staff members			

BUSINESS MODEL	Paid memberships plus products offered by members, e.g., Red Hat, over open source			
MEMBERSHIP	<p>Membership is corporate.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> nearly 250 Community members <p>Solicitation of Membership applications to corporations</p> <p>Paid memberships plus products offered by members, e.g., Red Hat, over open source</p>			
PROJECTS	Not clear, but there are “showcase” projects especially from the Community College Consortium for Open Educational Resources			
NUMBER OF CONTRIBUTORS	Approx. 300 contributions from 2013 through 2021 in database			
OPEN EDUCATION CONSORTIUM				
WEB SITE	https://www.oeconsortium.org/about-oe/			
ABOUT	The Open Education Consortium (OEC) is a non-profit, global, members-based network of open education institutions and organizations. OEC represents its members and provides advocacy and leadership around advancement of open education globally. OEC works with its members to build capacity to find, reuse, create and share Open Educational Resources (OER), develop open policy, create sustainable open education models, and enable international collaboration and innovation.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
GOVERNANCE MODEL	12-member Board, staff, 8-member staff			
BUSINESS MODEL	Fee-based, with nine categories, fees from 700 to 900 dollars			
MEMBERSHIP	OEC annually coordinates and hosts Open Education Week, the Open Education Global conference, and Open Education Awards for Excellence.			
PROJECTS	Not clear, but there are “showcase” projects especially from the Community College Consortium for Open Educational Resources			
OPEN HEALTH TOOLS				
WEB SITE	https://www.openhealthtools.org/			
ABOUT	Determined to be irrelevant – has nothing to do with OSS			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
OPEN MEDIA NOW / FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	Not available			
OPEN PLANNING FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://theopenplanningproject.org/			
OPEN SOURCE APPLICATIONS FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://www.osafoundation.org/			

ABOUT	OSAF is a non-profit organization working on Chandler Project, a Note-to-Self Organizer designed for personal and small-group task management and calendaring.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
BUSINESS MODEL	Non-profit, appears to have no income			
MEMBERSHIP	Very small			
PROJECTS	Single project called Chandler, for small group collaboration			
ONE LAPTOP PER CHILD ASSOCIATION INC.				
WEB SITE	http://www.laptop.org/			
ABOUT	Out of scope (nothing to do with OSS) The OLPC Foundation's mission is to stimulate local grassroots initiatives designed to enhance and sustain over time the effectiveness of laptops as learning tools for children living in lesser-developed countries.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
OSET INSTITUTE				
WEB SITE	https://www.osetinstitute.org			
ABOUT	Out of scope (nothing to do with OSS) Defenders of democracy. Democracy worldwide must be defended through trustworthy public election technology. To be trustworthy, public election technology must be verifiable, accurate, secure, and transparent. Trustworthiness of election technology compels a shift away from black-box proprietary toward glass-box public technology			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
SAHANA FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://sahanafoundation.org/			
ABOUT	Out of Scope Disaster Management			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
SHUTTLEWORTH FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://www.shuttleworthfoundation.org/			
ABOUT	Out of scope Investor			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
SOFTWARE LIVRE BRASIL				
WEB SITE	http://www.softwarelivre.org/			
ABOUT	Software TV YouTube Out of Scope			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	N

No longer in existence

Table 3: Organizations no longer in existence

FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION LATIN AMERICA				
WEB SITE	http://www.fossfa.net/			
ABOUT	It doesn't exist anymore			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	N
OPEN SOURCE FOR AMERICA				
WEB SITE	http://opensourceforamerica.org/about-osfa/our-mission/			
ABOUT	This foundation appears to no longer exist since 2019.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	N
OpenDOC SOCIETY				
WEB SITE	http://www.opendocsociety.org/			
ABOUT	Appears to no longer be operational.			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	N
PARROT FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	http://www.parrot.org/foundation/			
ABOUT	<p>U.S. (Washington State) non-profit foundation, incorporated to protect the intellectual property for the Parrot virtual machine, tools, libraries, and language implementations, while offering it for use under an open source license.</p> <p>NOTE: the foundation announced on 25 August 2021 that the Parrot VM is no longer being actively developed, and therefore the foundation has likely become inactive.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	Y	Y
GOVERNANCE MODEL	Board of directors elected in an annual meeting of the members.			
BUSINESS MODEL	Individual members do not appear to have fees; corporate sponsors (especially the BBC) pay yearly fees.			
MEMBERSHIP	Resources dedicated to developers of Parrot tools, etc. in order to encourage membership.			
PEER-DIRECTED PROJECTS CENTER (FREENODE)				
WEB SITE	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Freenode#Peer-Directed_Projects_Center			
ABOUT	<p>Ran the Freenode IRC network, where many prominent open source projects hosted their official IRC channels.</p> <p>In March 2013, the PDPC was dissolved. The decision to dissolve was made in part due to the donation levels and costs associated with maintaining its status as a charitable organization in the UK.</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N

PUBLIC SOFTWARE FUND				
WEB SITE	http://www.pubsoft.org/			
ABOUT	Does not Exist Anymore			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
SOFTWARE LIVRE ARGENTINA				
WEB SITE	http://solarargentina.org/			
ABOUT	Doesn't Exist Anymore			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	Y	N
SOFTWARE LIVRE CHILE				
WEB SITE	http://www.softwarelibrechile.cl/			
ABOUT	Not Working			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	N	Y	N	N
THE SOFTWARE CONSERVANCY				
WEB SITE	http://www.tsc.org/			
ABOUT	No Longer Operating			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	N
WIKIOTICS FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://wikiotics.org/en/Wikiotics_Foundation			
ABOUT	No Longer Operating			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y
ZOPE FOUNDATION				
WEB SITE	https://foundation.zope.dev/			
ABOUT	<p>The Zope Foundation has the goal to promote, maintain, and develop the Zope platform. It does this by supporting the Zope community. Our community includes the open source community of contributors to the Zope software, contributors to the documentation and web infrastructure, as well as the community of businesses and organizations that use Zope.</p> <p>Note – appears to be no longer active – latest update 2014</p>			
Scope	International	Independent	Transparency	Software Products
	Y	Y	N	Y